

Improving the FAIRness of vascular anomaly research data using the International Society for the Study of Vascular Anomalies (ISSVA) Ontology

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BACKGROUND

To support diagnosis, management, and further research of vascular anomalies, Mulliken and Glowacki created a comprehensive classification system for vascular anomalies [1]. The International Society for the Study of Vascular Anomalies (ISSVA, i.e., the society for specialists of various medical disciplines involved in the treatment of patients afflicted with vascular anomalies), adopted this classification in 1996. The current version of the classification is available as a PDF file, which does not allow for structured registration of these diagnoses using unique identifiers, nor implementation in software systems.

To make the data for vascular anomaly research more Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) [2], it is important that these diagnoses are registered in a structured and machine-readable manner. The Vascular Anomalies European Reference Network (VASCERN) and its Registry of Rare Vascular Anomalies (VASCA), therefore, adopted the ISSVA classification and created a machine-readable representation of the classification: the ISSVA ontology.

THE ISSVA ONTOLOGY

The ISSVA ontology describes vascular anomalies, the causal genes of such anomalies, and related vessels. The monohierarchical ontology is available in the Web Ontology Language (OWL) format at BioPortal (<https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/ISSVA>). The current version of ISSVA contains 202 concepts and 1126 axioms. The ontology is organized as a monohierarchy that has three main branches: Gene, Vascular anomaly, and

Vessel. The Gene branch contains all genes that are associated with one or more vascular anomalies. The Vascular anomaly branch contains all vascular anomalies that are either a vascular malformation or a vascular tumor. The Vessel branch contains all vessels that can be affected by a vascular anomaly. Additionally, mappings were added to concepts in the Orphanet Rare Disease Ontology (ORDO), National Cancer Institute thesaurus (NCIt), SNOMED Clinical Terms (SNOMED CT), the Human Phenotype Ontology (HPO), and the HUGO Gene Nomenclature (HGNC).

CURRENT APPLICATION OF THE ONTOLOGY

The ontology is currently implemented in an Electronic Data Capture system to support FAIR data collection and exposure for the Registry of Vascular Anomalies [3, 4]. In the registry, based on the European Platform on Rare Disease Registration's Set of Common Data Elements for rare disease registration, the diagnosis of the patient is registered using the ISSVA classification. The registered diagnosis is saved using the unique ISSVA concept identifier and the collected data are automatically transformed into a machine-readable representation (Figure 1). These machine-readable data can, subsequently, be queried using SPARQL queries.

Figure 1. Registering a machine-readable diagnosis

IMPLICATIONS FOR VASCULAR ANOMALY RESEARCH

The ISSVA ontology ensures that diagnoses of vascular anomalies can be recorded in a machine-readable format. These diagnoses were originally entered as free-text descriptions from classes in the ISSVA classification. The interoperability of clinical studies and registries that collect data for vascular anomaly research can be considerably improved by using a machine-readable version of the classification. Since the prevalence of most vascular anomalies is low, data is often distributed over various sources. Machine-readable data allow for the integration of data from several sources, improving the sample size and hence the data's power to execute valid analyses. We believe that the ontology will improve interoperability between clinical studies and registries, resulting in FAIRer vascular anomaly research.

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